

A SYSTEMATIC AGILE FRAMEWORK FOR TEST-DRIVEN ONTOLOGY VALIDATION IN ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE ANALYTICS AND DECISION-MAKING

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ABSTRACT

The rapid growth of educational data from diverse e-learning platforms such as Learning Management Systems (LMS) and Student Information Systems (SIS) presents challenges for universities in integrating and analyzing this data to monitor student performance, assess course effectiveness, and optimize faculty resource allocation. Ontologies provide a robust framework for enabling semantic interoperability and facilitating the integration of heterogeneous data sources for Learning Analytics (LA) and decision-making purposes. This study introduces the SPC_Academic_Performance ontology, a domain-specific ontology developed to consolidate and analyze academic performance data. To ensure the reliability and accuracy of the SPC_Academic_Performance ontology, we adopt the Test-Driven Development Ontology (TDDOnto2) methodology. TDDOnto2 systematically integrates validation techniques into the ontology development process, focusing on consistency checking and property testing. By applying TDDOnto2, this study aims to address common challenges such as logical inconsistencies and incomplete property definitions, ensuring the ontology's robustness for data integration and retrieval. The findings contribute to developing a systematic ontology validation framework that supports reliable ontology-driven analytics and informed decision-making in higher education. This approach ensures that the proposed ontology can effectively map and retrieve data from heterogeneous sources, ultimately enhancing the accuracy and utility of Learning Analytics in academic performance monitoring and resource management.

Keywords: *Learning Analytics, University Ontologies, Data Retrieval Model, Ontologies Evaluation, Ontologies Validation, Web Semantic Ontology*

1. INTRODUCTION

The fast pace of digitalisation brought advancements to higher education, which significantly changed the ways in which educational institutions collect, manage, analyse, and use data [1], [2], [3]. E-learning platforms, such as Learning Management Systems (LMS)

and Student Information Systems (SIS), serve as core tools for facilitating education and producing vast amounts of heterogeneous data. This data consists of various metrics, including student grades, attendance records, course evaluations, and resource allocations. While the use of such data can enhance decision-making processing, there are technical and semantic complexities

when integrating data across various platforms [2], [4], [5]. Not only SQL (NoSQL) graph databases are a type of NoSQL database that is built to handle data structures that are very complicated and highly connected [6]. These databases store the data in the form of nodes, edges, and properties, which are very convenient as a relationship within these educational datasets. By integrating NoSQL graph databases with ontologies, institutions can enhance their capacity to manage and query interconnected data, creating a robust foundation for Learning Analytics and decision-making [4]. Ontology-based systems have been seen as the answer to these problems, providing a way of defining how data is represented and improving the ability to integrate data from different systems [1], [4], [7].

The semantic web enriches the integration process by facilitating a "Web of Data." Technologies like RDF (Resource Description Framework) and OWL (Web Ontology Language) play a critical role in enabling semantic annotations and logical reasoning over data [8], [9]. OWL provides formal language constructs to define classes, properties, and relationships, enabling precise knowledge representation [10], [11]. The SPC_Academic_Performance ontology, designed within this framework, consolidates data from multiple e-learning platforms to provide a unified foundation for analyzing academic performance and optimizing resource allocation [12], [13]. However, guaranteeing the trustworthiness and precision of such an ontology is essential for its effectiveness. Logical inconsistencies, incomplete property definitions, and inadequate testing can compromise its effectiveness and usability [2], [4].

Most conventional approaches to ontology development lack thorough validation procedures and typically provide only basic validation features tools [14], which may result in undetected errors and reduced stakeholder confidence [4]. In contrast, TDDOnto2 offers enhanced accuracy over standard ontology editors [14] and introduces an agile, test-driven approach to ontology development. It allows researchers to create and execute validation tests before or during the modeling process to ensure correctness throughout. Meaning that researchers

can iteratively refine their Description Logic (DL) constructs until all tests are fully passed. Furthermore, the tool integrates a regression algorithm which enhances ontology validation accuracy while producing dependable results.

To address these gaps, this research uses TDDOnto2, a test-driven development framework to check the viability of an ontology known as SPC_Academic_Performance. It is evaluated for logical content and property checking to ensure that all class taxonomical structures, well cardinalities, and object property connections exactly reflect the semantics of the relevant domain as stated. The methodology introduces a systematic structured testing process that will assess the ontology via consistency checks, property validations, and individual test cases to finalise the evaluation. This research shows how TDDOnto2 can be used in practice as evidenced by the enhancement of the quality of the ontology by the framework.

The research contributes clear guidelines for practical ontology validation that offer agile regression testing to make validation processes more dependable and manageable. This research also reveals challenges and effective ways of employing TDDOnto2 in ontology validation, thereby providing other scholars and developers with similar approach. This work moves the field of ontology engineering forward by breaking the research down into the design and validation phases, making certain that the ontologies produced are correct in their semantics, as well as effective in the contexts in which they are to be used. In previous study [15], a variant of Student Performance and Course Performance (SPC) OWL ontology named SPC_Academic_Performance was introduced in learning analytics (LA) to study the heterogeneous pattern of student and course performance. Hence, this paper aims to validate the SPC_Academic_Performance ontology developed earlier. The validation will assess the ontology via consistency checks, property validations, and individual test cases to finalise the evaluation.

The following sections of this paper are structured as follows: Section 1 provides an overview of some of the ontologies validation

techniques available, as well as how the DL is applied to integrate and link all the heterogeneous data and motivation to use the TDDonto2 in the study. Section 2 defines the structure of the SPC_Academic_Performance ontology and the configuration established for testing. Section 3 presents the results and interpretation of the test, while Section 4 offers the study's conclusion.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Current Practices in Ontology Validation

With an increasing number of ontologies, there is an increasing demand for innovative tools and methodologies to achieve consistency among various information representations. This is also applicable to the approach of validating the ontologies. Researchers employ various tools and techniques to validate the ontologies. The assessment may include checking the class and subclass definition errors, class redundancy errors, and class linkage errors. The class linkage error occurs when the relationship or the object properties set among the Subject, Predicate, and Object are insufficient to complete the triples.

The tool like OntoAnalyser [16], Onto Generator [16], OntoClean [16], OntoVal [17], ONE-T [16], and Ontology Pitfall Scanner! (OOPS!) [16] are quite common to be used in the validation process. A study by [16] evaluated the performance of several commonly available ontology validation tools. As for OOPS!, it operates by utilising a predefined catalog of pitfalls, which are categorised based on their severity: critical, important, and minor to allow users to prioritise issues effectively [18]. The OOPS! is also quite common to be used in the area of ontologies that belong to LA domain where it serves to validate the ontologies for the semantic representation of syllabuses ontology (OntoSyllabus) [19], Curriculum Course Syllabus Ontology (CCSO) [20] and, Ontology for Linked Open University Data (OLOUD) [21], [22].

To increase the efficiency of the ontologies produced, some studies implemented the Competency Question (CQ), which is a set of questions that are used to evaluate the quality of the ontology based on the SPARQL result generated [20], [21], [22], [23]. To determine the accuracy of the constructed ontology, the results retrieved from the data retrieval must align with the expectations of the domain expert. Studies conducted by [24], [25], [26], [27] proposed an enhanced data retrieval framework incorporating an additional layer that

leverages SPARQL query generation from RDF-based ontologies, with performance assessed through evaluation metrics including accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score.

2.2 Description Logic in Semantic Data Retrieval

To define the structure of data, a data model is needed for this purpose. The common data model that we heard about is the Entity Relationship Diagram (ERD), which is being used widely in Relational Database Management Systems (RDBMS). The concept of the ERD is somewhat analogous to OWL semantic modelling. However, the ERD and OWL semantic models serve diverse data representation and knowledge management functions [28]. ERDs are primarily utilised in database design to visually depict the relationships between entities within a system, focusing on the structure of data and how different entities interact with one another. In contrast, OWL is a formal language intended for the representation of intricate and comprehensive knowledge concerning entities, collections of entities, and their interrelations inside the semantic web.

In an OWL, Description Logic (DL) performs critical support for important reasoning services in ontology-based systems. For example, reasoning about class hierarchies, property characteristics, or the relationships between instances can be done using DL reasoners, which are unique algorithms for managing the tough semantics of DL [29], [30]. These DL reasoners can determine the satisfiability, entailment, and consistency of ontologies, which are essential for ensuring the correctness and reliability of knowledge representation in OWL [31], [32]. Additionally, it has been investigated to improve the expressiveness and application of OWL in various areas by integrating DL into other computational paradigms, such as rules and probabilistic reasoning [33], [34].

In the context of OWL, DL serves as the underlying framework that defines the semantics of the language. OWL is designed to facilitate the creation of ontologies that can be shared and reused across different applications on the Semantic Web. Specifically, OWL Lite and OWL DL are based on specific DLs, such as base SHIF(D) and a more advanced SHOIN(D), respectively [33]. In this study, all the axioms tested in the TDDOonto2 plugin use the SHIF(D) language.

Figure 2: SPC_Academic_Performance ontology class hierarchy

The object properties carefully defined and structured within the SPC_Academic_Performance ontology, along with their domains and ranges of the triples, are comprehensively detailed in Table 2 below.

Table 2: List of class (subject, predicate) and relationship object properties utilised in SPC_Academic_Performance ontology

#	Object properties (P)	Subject (S) / Domain	Object (O) / Range
1	is a	Person	Student
2	is a	Person	Lecturer
3	consist of	University	Faculty
4	has attendance	Student	Attendance
5	has grade	Student	Grade
6	has messagepost	Student	Messagepost
7	has semester	Student	Semester
8	has semester	Course	Semester
9	undergraduate type	Student	Studylevel
10	undergraduate type	Course	Studylevel
11	has cohort	Student	Cohort
12	has cohort	Course	Cohort
13	enrols	Student	Course
14	attached to	Student	Group
15	belong to	Student	Faculty
16	belong to	Lecturer	Faculty
17	teach	Lecturer	Group
18	teach	Lecturer	Course
19	offer	Faculty	Course
20	offered in	Course	Group
21	has assessment	Course	Assessment
22	has programme	Course	Programme
23	has gradecount	Course	Gradecount
24	optional to have	Course	Prerequisite
21	has assessment	Course	Assessment

In the tested relationship object properties, several object properties: such as ‘is_a’, ‘has_semester’, ‘undergraduate_type’, ‘has_cohort’, ‘belong_to’ and ‘teach’ are used more than once as the exact relationship is employed to link two distinct domains to a single range, following OWL regulations. For instance, using properties such as ‘owl: ObjectProperty’ enables the establishment of relationships between instances of different classes. This means that two distinct classes can have properties that point to the same instance of a third class, effectively allowing multiple domains to

connect to a single range class. This is particularly useful in scenarios where different entities share common characteristics or attributes, facilitating interoperability and integration across diverse domains [41], [42]. By utilising TDDonto2, the ontology was subjected to automated reasoning processes to detect potential logical conflicts or inconsistencies arising from incorrect class hierarchies, improperly defined relationships, or ambiguous constraints.

3.2. Testing Setup

3.2.1. Consistency Check

In this study, the consistency of the developed ontology was rigorously evaluated using the TDDonto2 plugin integrated within Protégé, a widely used ontology development environment. The consistency test aimed to ensure that the logical structure of the ontology adhered to formal reasoning principles, mainly focusing on the hierarchical relationships among classes and subclasses.

Table 3: Example test scenario for consistency check

Consistency Test	Validation Formula	Result	Comments
Class Hierarchy	$\forall x (Lecturer(x) \rightarrow Person(x))$	Consistent	Subclass relationships valid
Class Hierarchy	$\forall x (Student(x) \rightarrow Person(x))$	Consistent	Subclass relationships valid
Class Hierarchy	$\forall x (University(x) \rightarrow Person(x))$	Not Consistent	Subclass relationships are not valid

According to the example in Table 3, two hierarchy elements are consistent, as indicated in Figure 2; the class 'Lecturer' and 'Person' are subclasses of the class 'Person'. Simultaneously, the University does not constitute a subclass of Person, indicating a lack of subclass relationship.

3.2.2. Property Validation

Simultaneously, property validation is conducted to examine the correlation of object properties defined in the ontology, ensuring that these properties are accurately defined with suitable domains, ranges, and characteristics (functional and cardinality). The cardinality values employed are determined by the guidelines established during the interview with the domain expert early in the ontology's creation. Examples of functionality and cardinality are illustrated in the following example:

3.2.2.1. Functional

Table 4: Example test scenario for functional property validation

Scenario	Entities	Object Property	Relation
1	Lecture → Person	is_a	The lecturer is a Person
2	Course → Lecturer	teach	Lecturers teach the Course
3	Assessment → Course	has_assessment	The course has an Assessment

3.2.2.2. Cardinality

Table 5: Example test scenario for cardinality property validation

Scenario	Description	DL Axiom	Relation
Minimum Cardinality	Specifies the minimum number of instances allowed	Student $\sqsubseteq \exists$ enrolls.Course $\sqcap \geq 1$ enrolls.Course	Each student may enrol in a minimum of one course per semester
Maximum Cardinality	Specifies the maximum number of instances allowed	Lecturer $\sqsubseteq \exists$ belong_to.Faculty $\sqcap \leq 2$ belong_to.Faculty	Each lecturer can belong to not more than two faculty
Exact Cardinality	Specifies the exact number of instances allowed	Student $\sqsubseteq \exists$ belong_to.Faculty $\sqcap = 1$ belong_to.Faculty	Each student can belong to only one faculty

Each tested axiom will be sequentially incorporated into the TDDonto2 test list, culminating in a comprehensive evaluation of all axioms collectively.

Figure 3: TDDonto2 test flow

If the axiom(s) already exists, the tool will directly ascertain their existence to prevent redundancy of the textual axioms. If axioms are logically correct, the result will indicate entailed; otherwise, it will fail (inconsistent, incoherent, absent). In TDDonto2 testing, only axiom(s) "entailed" yield a pass result, while all other cases produce failures [14].

Given consistent and coherent ontology O , and an axiom A s.t. $\Sigma(A) \subseteq \Sigma(O)$, i.e.,

$$pre-test_O(A) = \begin{cases} O \not\vdash \perp & \text{ontology is consistent} \\ C \in V_C \text{ s.t. } C \sqsubseteq \neg \perp & \text{ontology is coherent} \\ \Sigma(A) \subseteq \Sigma(O) & \text{axiom vocabulary elements present in } O \end{cases}$$

Then, the result of testing O against A is:

$$test_O(A) = \begin{cases} \text{entailed} & \text{if } O \vdash A \\ \text{inconsistent} & \text{if } O \cup A \vdash \perp \\ \text{incoherent} & \text{if } O \cup A \not\vdash \perp \wedge (\exists C \in \Sigma_C(O)) \wedge O \cup A \vdash C \sqsubseteq \perp \\ \text{absent} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

Figure 4: TDDonto2 regression testing logic [14]

In a more straightforward explanation, the axiom(s) must first be present in the ontology during the *pre-testo(A)*, including relevant classes, relationships, or properties, to ensure accurate reasoning and determine if the results are entailed.

The knowledge or axioms are generated based on test-based, test-last [43], and test-first approaches [44] that are often associated with test-driven development. Some axiom(s) for the tests are created before the tests are conducted, and there is a case that some of the axiom(s) are made after the test is run. If there is an error or missing condition, this axiom will be added or modified after the test [39]. The testing cycle ends when all test results fulfill the axioms and entailed.

This study's axiom(s) is tested using the HermiT 1.4.3.456 reasoner. The researcher must revise the axiom(s) if an error occurs during the configuration of the DL and axiom(s). This testing method is adapted from the study of [39]. The test is executed based on Figure 3 above.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1. Result of the Consistency Check

The axioms utilised for testing the consistency check of the class and subclass structures within the ontology are comprehensively

listed in Table 6 below. Additionally, the axioms outlined in Table 7 are designed to validate the properties and their relationships within the ontology. Together, these tests play a critical role in verifying the structural and semantic correctness of the ontology, ensuring it adheres to its intended design principles.

Table 6: List of axioms and results for consistency check

#	Class Hierarchy DL	TDDonto2 Axiom	Relation	Result test:	
				1	2
1	Student \sqsubseteq Person	Student SubClassOf : Person	“Student” is a subclass of “Person”	✓	✓
2	Lecturer \sqsubseteq Person	Lecturer SubClassOf : Person	“Lecturer” is a subclass of “Person”	✓	✓
3	Attendance \sqsubseteq Student	Attendance SubClassOf : Student	“Attendance” is a subclass of “Student”	✓	✓
4	Grade \sqsubseteq Student	Grade SubClassOf : Student	“Grade” is a subclass of “Student”	✓	✓
5	Messagepost \sqsubseteq Student	Messagepost SubClassOf : Student	“Messagepost” is a subclass of “Student”	✓	✓
6	Semester \sqsubseteq Student	Semester SubClassOf : Student	“Semester” is a subclass of “Student”	✓	✓
7	Studylevel \sqsubseteq Student	Studylevel SubClassOf : Student	“Studylevel” is a subclass of “Student”	✓	✓
8	Faculty \sqsubseteq University	Faculty SubClassOf : University	“Faculty” is a subclass of “University”	✓	✓
9	Course \sqsubseteq Faculty	Course SubClassOf : Faculty	“Course” is a subclass of “Faculty”	✓	✓
10	Assessment \sqsubseteq Course	Assessment SubClassOf : Course	“Assessment” is a subclass of “Course”	✓	✓
11	Cohort \sqsubseteq Course	Cohort SubClassOf : Course	“Cohort” is a subclass of “Course”	✓	✓
12	Gradecount \sqsubseteq Course	Gradecount SubClassOf : Course	“Gradecount” is a subclass of “Course”	✓	✓
13	Group \sqsubseteq Course	Group SubClassOf : Course	“Group” is a subclass of “Course”	✓	✓
14	Prerequisite \sqsubseteq Course	Prerequisite SubClassOf : Course	“Prerequisite” is a subclass of “Course”	✓	✓

			subclass of “Course”		
15	Programme \sqsubseteq Course	Programme SubClassOf : Course	“Programme” is a subclass of “Course”	✓	✓

Note: Consistent = ✓, not consistent = X

Figure 4: Axioms execution for consistency check

The tests were conducted twice for consistency check, and both tests demonstrated that all of the subclass hierarchy of the evaluated ontology is consistent. Figure 4 shows the result of the consistency check on the ontology structure, and as seen from the result, all the subclasses have ‘Entailed’ results with the superclass it links to. The series of tests will stop once all of the axiom(s) succeed.

4.2. Result of the property validation

4.2.1. Functional

To test the object properties functionality between the subject and object for each relationship, a set of 24 axioms are created and executed, and the test results are illustrated in Table 7 below.

Table 7: List of axioms and results for functional property validation

#	Object Property	TDDonto2 Axiom	Result test:	
			1	2
1	is_a	Person SubClassOf: is_a some Student	✓	✓
2	is_a	Person SubClassOf: is_a some Lecturer	✓	✓
3	consist_of	University SubClassOf: consist_of some Faculty	✓	✓
4	has_attendance	Student SubClassOf: has_attendance some Attendance	✓	✓
5	has_grade	Student SubClassOf: has_grade some Grade	✓	✓
6	has_messagepost	Student SubClassOf: has_messagepost some Messagepost	✓	✓
7	has_semester	Student SubClassOf: has_semester some Semester	✓	✓

8	has_semester	Course SubClassOf: has_semester some Semester	✓	✓
9	Undergraduate_type	Student SubClassOf: undergraduate_type some Studylevel	✓	✓
10	Undergraduate_type	Course SubClassOf: undergraduate_type some Studylevel	✓	✓
11	has_cohort	Course SubClassOf: undergraduate_type some Studylevel	X	✓
12	has_cohort	Student SubClassOf: has_cohort some Cohort	X	✓
13	enrols	Course SubClassOf: has_cohort some Cohort	✓	✓
14	attached_to	Student SubClassOf: enrols some Course	✓	✓
15	belong_to	Student SubClassOf: attached_to some Group	✓	✓
16	belong_to	Lecturer SubClassOf: belong_to some Faculty	✓	✓
17	teach	Lecturer SubClassOf: teach some Group	✓	✓
18	teach	Lecturer SubClassOf: teach some Course	✓	✓
19	offer	Faculty SubClassOf: offer some Course	✓	✓
20	offered_in	Course SubClassOf: offered_in some Group	✓	✓
21	has_assessment	Course SubClassOf: has_assessment some Assessment	✓	✓
22	has_programme	Course SubClassOf: has_programme some Programme	✓	✓
23	has_gradecount	Course SubClassOf: has_gradecount some Gradecount	✓	✓
24	optional_to_have	Course SubClassOf: optional_to_have some Prerequisite	✓	✓

Note: Pass = ✓, not pass =X

Initially, when the axioms are incorporated into the TDDonto2 test list, the outcome will be indicated as ‘Absent’. The relationship must be added to the active ontology. In the initial Test 1, both object properties for 'has_cohort' axioms include spelling errors in the syntax determination. However, this error has been rectified in Test 2. Figure 5 below shows the result of the functional of the ontology structure. The result shows that all the relationship and cardinality tests have ‘Entailed’ results.

Figure 5: Axioms execution for functional validation

4.2.2. Cardinality

Meanwhile, for the cardinality, all the five cardinalities tested returned green colour passed but “Absent” results as illustrated in Table 8 and Figure 6 for Test 1.

Table 8: List of axioms and results for functional property validation

#	Object Property	TDDonto2 Axiom	Result test: 1
1	belong_to	Student SubClassOf belong_to exactly 1 Faculty	✓ (Absent)
2	enrols	Student SubClassOf: enrols some Course and enrols min 1 Course	✓ (Absent)
3	has_assessment	Course SubClassOf: has_assessment some Assessment and has_assessment min 1 Assessment	✓ (Absent)
4	teach	Lecturer SubClassOf: teach some Group and teach min 1 Group	✓ (Absent)
5	teach	Lecturer SubClassOf: teach some Course and teach min 1 Course	✓ (Absent)

Note: Pass = ✓, not pass =X

Figure 6: Axioms execution for Test 1 cardinality validation

Concerning the cardinality test from Test 1, a specific new individual is created in each of the axiom(s) classes. This individual is used and acts as an entity to fulfil the cardinality condition. The same axiom(s) are tested again in the second test, the result of which is illustrated in Table 9.

Table 9: List of Test 2 results for cardinality property validation after modification

#	Object Property	TDDonto2 Axiom	Result test: 2
1	belong_to	Student SubClassOf belong_to exactly 1 Faculty	✓ (Entailed)
2	enrols	Student SubClassOf: enrols some Course and enrols min 1 Course	✓ (Entailed)
3	has_assessment	Course SubClassOf: has_assessment some Assessment and has_assessment min 1 Assessment	✓ (Entailed)
4	teach	Lecturer SubClassOf: teach some Group and teach min 1 Group	✓ (Entailed)
5	teach	Lecturer SubClassOf: teach some Course and teach min 1 Course	✓ (Entailed)

Note: Pass = ✓, not pass =X

Figure 7 below shows the result of the functional and cardinality of the ontology structure. The result shows that all the relationship and cardinality tests have ‘Entailed’ results.

Figure 7: Axioms execution for Test 2 cardinality validation

4.2.3. Result Summary

The values shown in Table 9 illustrate the testing outcomes of two sets of testing performed using TDDonto2, covering the aspect of consistency check and property validation (functional and cardinality characteristics). All the 12 consistency checks were completed in Test 1 and Test 2 successfully with a 100% success rate, hence the consistency ratio of 1. This indicates that the ontology's hierarchical and logical structure of SPC_Academic_Performance is robust and error-free across iterations. While validating the properties, the functional aspect included 24 tests in total. Test 1 yields 22 tests passed on the first try, while test 2 passed all the 24 tests. This resulted into Test 1 which yielded a success rate of 95.8% and

Test 2 which had a success rate of 100, and in sum the average consistency ratio of 0.92. For the Cardinality aspect, five tests were accomplished as desired for both set, with a 100% pass rate and 1.0 consistency ratio.

Table 10: Result summary

Validity Aspect	Total Test	Test 1 (Pass)	Test 2 (Pass)	SR (%)	CR
Consistency Checks	12	12	12	100	1.0
Property Validations: Functional	24	22	24	95.8	0.92
Property Validations: Cardinality	5	5	5	100	1.0

Note: Success Rate = SR, Consistency Ratio =CR

These results underline the reliability of the ontology in adhering to logical consistency and property validation requirements. The incremental improvement in the functional property validations demonstrates the effectiveness of iterative debugging and refinement, which is a hallmark of test-driven ontology development. The high levels, success rates, and consistency ratios are a testament to the ontology capability to cater to real-world LA applications.

5. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORKS

This study tested the proposed SPC_Academic_Performance ontology reliability and validity using TDDonto2 based on two approaches, primarily testing for consistency checks and property validations (functional and cardinality aspects). The results have confirmed the efficiency of the established ontology structure since all the consistency checks tested on two sets equal 1, showing that the structure is logical and consistent. The success rate for functional property validation also improved from 95.83% in the first test to 100% in the second, showcasing the iterative refinement of the ontology during testing. Cardinality validation consistently maintained a 100% success rate across all tests, reflecting a robust implementation of constraints such as relationships and cardinality rules. As this ontology is developed based on the thematic analysis, with classes and subclasses derived from the CQ. The data retrieved from this ontology will be validated by a domain expert to confirm its alignment with their expectations. This presents an opportunity to examine the data

extracted from the proposed ontology with example data sourced directly from the academic performance of students and courses at selected universities. These findings can confirm that the ontology can meet domain-specific requirements while ensuring scalability and reliability for real-world LA applications and data retrieval, especially in analysing the university student and course performance. The current study can be interpreted as the first step in data retrieval validation. Future research could explore the accuracy of data retrieval by applying real-world learner analytics (LA) data and evaluating the results using a confusion matrix to measure accuracy, precision, recall, and F1 score of the data retrieved from the SPC_Academic_Performance ontology.

The guidelines presented in this study can offer direction for ontology validation through agile test-driven methods, addressing consistency and validity tests, which can be applied not only to learning analytics but also to other data retrieval application fields like biological research, artificial intelligence, banking, and healthcare.

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